

INSTITUTIONAL MORAL HARASSMENT AT THE WORKPLACE. POSSIBILITY OF ADOPTING SOLUTIONS DEVELOPED IN FRENCH JURISPRUDENCE WITHIN THE NATIONAL LEGAL FRAMEWORK OF ROMANIA.

PhD. Răzvan, Anghel
Judge, Constanța Court of Appeal

Abstract:

Workplace harassment, with relatively recent regulation in Romania, from the year 2020, is a form of discrimination that is continuously evolving, constantly adopting new forms, and courts are being called upon in new and increasingly numerous cases to rule on the existence of such behaviour by the employer or other employees.

Recently, the French Court of Cassation ruled on a specific form of workplace harassment, namely institutional harassment. Essentially, this consists of a programmed behaviour by the employer aimed at deteriorating the work environment, with the ultimate goal of reducing the number of employees while avoiding dismissal procedures.

The article presents the decision of the French supreme court and explores the possibilities of using the concept of institutional harassment in the workplace within the Romanian legal framework.

Keywords: *workplace harassment; deterioration of the work environment.*

I. Introduction

Harassment at the workplace received a new regulation in Romania in 2020 through Law No 151/2020 and Law No 167/2020, which amended the Labour Code and Government Ordinance No 137/2000. Of course, it would have been preferable to have a single normative act to bring these legislative changes, especially since they took place in the same year, and a single normative act to include the regulation of this type of discrimination, so that in practice there is no longer always the present problem of correlating some legal provisions from different normative acts, with various results, not always predictable.

It should be noted that the new definitions start from the definition given to harassment in Article 2(3) of Directive 2000/78/EC, according to which " *Harassment shall be deemed to be a form of discrimination within the meaning of paragraph 1, when unwanted conduct related to any of the grounds referred to in Article 1 takes place with the purpose or effect of violating the dignity of a person and of creating an intimidating, hostile, degrading,*

humiliating or offensive environment". This legislative text expressly states that "[i]n this context, the concept of harassment may be defined in accordance with the national laws and practice of the Member States."

Thus, Law No. 151/2020 supplemented Article 5 of the Romanian Labour Code with a par. (5) defining harassment in labour relations, which consists of any type of behaviour based on one of the criteria set out in par. (2) and which has the purpose or effect of violating the dignity of a person and leads to the creation of an intimidating, hostile, degrading, humiliating or offensive environment.

Law No. 167/2020 supplemented Article 2 of Government Ordinance No. 137/2000 with paragraphs (5¹) to (5⁷) regulating moral harassment in the workplace.

The new Romanian regulation defines two forms of harassment in the workplace:

(1) any behavior exercised with respect to an employee that has the purpose or effect of a deterioration of the working conditions by violating the rights or dignity of the employee, by affecting his physical or mental health or by compromising his professional future, behavior manifested in any of the following forms: a) hostile or undesirable conduct; b) verbal comments; c) actions or gestures (in par. (5¹));

(2) any behavior that, by its systematic nature, may prejudice the dignity, physical or mental integrity of an employee or group of employees, endangering their work or degrading the working climate; stress and physical exhaustion fall under the incidence of moral harassment at work (in par. (5²)); for the purposes of this legal text, stress and physical exhaustion fall within the scope of psychological harassment in the workplace.

From the legal provisions mentioned, it would seem, at first glance, that harassment at work concerns employees individually, with the exception of the one regulated in par. (5²) of Art. 2 of G.O. No. 137/2000, which expressly refers to groups of employees.

Even so, it still seems that harassment in the workplace would, in principle, have a specific 'target', even if it is a group of employees, such as members of a trade union organisation or members of an ethnic group, etc.

Recently, however, the question has been raised in French judicial practice as to whether harassment in the workplace can be of an 'institutional' nature in the sense that it is the result of a company management policy and targets all employees, possibly with some exceptions; the purpose of such action may be to reduce staff 'voluntarily' in order to avoid complicated and costly collective redundancy procedures, so that, by deteriorating the working environment, many employees are 'convinced' to terminate the employment relationship on their own initiative, thereby also depriving them of the compensatory rights to which they would have been entitled if they had been dismissed for reasons unrelated to them.

II. The French case-law solution

In a very recent judgment of 21 January 2025,¹ the French Court of Cassation established the possibility of a type of *institutional moral harassment in the workplace* that can be classified under the notion of harassment in the workplace provided by law.

¹ Cour de cassation, Pourvoi No 22-87.145, Chambre criminelle - Formation de section, ECLI:FR:CCASS:2025:CR00003, Source: <https://www.courdecassation.fr/en/decision/678f6a5a29d9a5b0535ebb19> (accessed 23.03.2025);

The problem was more difficult than it seems because, as regards the criminal liability that French law provides for harassment in the workplace, it was first examined whether such a conclusion meets the requirements of the principle of legality of criminal offences that is applicable in criminal matters, from the perspective of the predictability of criminal law.

At the same time, this problem also resulted from the fact that the legal text refers, like the Romanian rule, to treatments applied to persons and not to a group of persons, a defence invoked in this case.²

Even under these circumstances, the French Court of Cassation held that this type of ‘institutional’ harassment at the workplace is also prohibited by law.

In the grounds of the judgment cited, the following were also stated:³

29. Article 222-33-2 of the Criminal Code, in the version applicable to the facts of the case, derived from Law No 2002-73 of 17 January 2002, known as the Law on Social Modernisation, criminalises the act of harassing others by repeated acts the object or effect of which is to impair their rights and dignity, impair their physical or mental health or compromise their professional future.

30. That provision thus distinguishes actions which have as their object a deterioration in working conditions from those which have such an effect.

31. The characterisation of actions resulting in a deterioration of working conditions presupposes the precise identification of the victims of such actions. On the other hand, where the acts of harassment have as their object such degradation, the characterisation of the offence does not require that the acts of which the perpetrator is accused relate to one or more employees in a direct relationship with him or her, or that the victim employees are designated individually. In fact, in that situation, the formal nature of the offence does not imply a finding of an actual deterioration in working conditions.

32. Similarly, the term ‘others’ may, in the absence of any other indication, refer to a group of employees not individually identified.

33. That interpretation is consistent with the purpose which the legislature intended to give to that criminalisation.

34. In fact, although the travaux préparatoires for Law No 2002-73 of 17 January 2002 referred to above do not specifically address the issue of collective or institutional psychological harassment, they refer to the fact that an opinion of the National Consultative Commission on Human Rights of 29 June 2000, dedicated to psychological harassment in the workplace, was ‘carefully acquainted’ with it.

² French Criminal Code (version applicable in the case, in force from 18.01.2002 to 08.08.2012, adopted by Law No 2002-73 of 17.01.2002, Art. 170, JORF 18 janvier 2002, known as the Social Modernisation Law)

‘Article 222-33-2

Le fait de harceler autrui par des agissements répétés ayant pour objet ou pour effet une dégradation des conditions de travail susceptible de porter atteinte à ses droits et à sa dignité, d’altérer sa santé physique ou mentale ou de compromettre son avenir professionnel, est puni d’un an d’emprisonnement et de 15000 euros d’amende’.

[Acts of harassment of other persons by repeated conduct, the object or effect of which is to impair working conditions, which may adversely affect their rights and dignity, affect their physical or mental health or compromise their professional future, shall be punishable by one year’s imprisonment and a fine of EUR 15,000.]

Source: <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/codes/id/LEGIARTI000006417711/2002-01-18/> (accessed 23.03.2025)

³ translation done through the European Commission’s eTranslation service <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/etranslation> and reviewed by the author;

35. *This opinion identified three possible forms of psychological harassment: individual harassment, practiced with a purely gratuitous purpose of destroying others and valuing one's own power; organised professional harassment of one or more specifically designated employees intended to circumvent statutory dismissal procedures; and institutional harassment as part of a management strategy for all staff.*

36. *In addition, requested by the Prime Minister to conduct a reflection on psychological harassment in the workplace, following a first debate at the National Assembly on the subject, the Economic and Social Council, in an opinion of 11 April 2001, distinguished between 'harassment essentially of an individual or a small group' and 'collective, professional or institutional harassment, which thus forms part of a real management strategy in order to impose new operating rules, new missions or new returns', stating that 'moral harassment may then occur in times of restructuring, mergers and absorptions of private undertakings or changes in management orientation' (Opinion of the Economic and Social Council, 11 April 2001, page 52).*

37. *In the same document, it proposed the definition of the offence of psychological harassment in the workplace as 'all repeated actions aimed at degrading the human, relational or working material conditions of one or more victims, liable to affect their rights and dignity, which could seriously alter their state of health and compromise their professional future', stating that that definition took account of all instances of psychological harassment in the workplace.*

38. *Commenting on the terms of the proposed definition of "one or more victims", the Economic and Social Council stressed that "if psychological harassment in the workplace most often affects a single person, who becomes the target of the actions of a single perpetrator or perpetrators, it is not uncommon for the process to target several victims at the same time. This is often the case with an overall strategy for imposing new management methods in order to obtain the resignation of staff whose characteristics (e.g. age) do not correspond to the 'needs' of the company. It may also be abusive individual behaviour by the employer' (mentioned opinion, pages 59 and 60). [...]*

40. *Consequently, the legal element of the offence of psychological harassment does not require repeated actions to be directed against a specific victim or in the context of interpersonal relations between their perpetrator and the victim or victims, provided that the latter belong to the same working community and were likely to suffer or have suffered the consequences referred to in Article 222-33-2 of the Criminal Code.*

41. *Irrespective of any considerations relating to the strategic choices made by the company's decision-making bodies, actions which are covered by the provisions of Article 222-33-2 of the Criminal Code, in the version resulting from Law No 2002-73 of 17 January 2002, and which may characterise a situation of institutional psychological harassment, are actions which seek to decide and implement, knowingly, an undertaking policy aimed at the deterioration of the working conditions of all or part of the employees, with a view to reducing their staff or achieving any other objective, whether managerial, economic or financial, or which has the effect of such a deterioration, liable to affect the rights and dignity of those employees, to affect their physical or mental health or to compromise their professional future.*

[...]

69. *In order to find Mr [XG] and Mr [FS] guilty of psychological harassment for the period retained by the criminal court, namely from 1 January 2007 to 31 December 2008, the contested decision states that it is necessary to examine whether those defendants may be held liable for such an offence not because of their individual relations with their employees, but because of the company policy which they have devised and implemented.*

70. *The judges state that, although the appropriateness of such a policy, which comes under the power of direction, escapes their assessment, they must examine the method used to implement it, in order to determine whether it exceeds the normal powers of direction and control of the director of the undertaking.*

71. *Examining the objective of the NExT plan, they explain, for their own reasons and themselves, that, in order to ensure profitable growth of the company, that plan was based, inter alia, on a policy of staff reduction which, although initially not the case, had as its object, since October 2006, the degradation of working conditions in order to compel employees to accept mobility or to leave the workplace.*

72. *They note that this policy, which was based on creating an anxious climate, resulted in the implementation of three specific actions: pressure on departure control in tracking staff at all levels of the chain of command, including departures in the criteria for remuneration of management team members and conditioning the intermediate hierarchy to staff reduction during the training sessions offered.*

73. *They note that these actions, which went far beyond the normal powers of direction and control of a leader, continued and repeated over the next two years and that, by their very nature, they constitute repeated actions that deliberately aimed at the degradation of working conditions.*

74. *They note that the most serious mistake was the transition from an indicative to an imperative objective, which had to be achieved 'at all costs', while employees, mostly civil servants, could not be subject to an economic redundancy process, which created an anxious climate for all staff, once the 'crisis programme', designed to accelerate natural retirement movements, was validated, in accordance with a decision taken at the highest level of the company's management.*

75. *They also point out that due to the pressure resulting from these actions, inseparable from them, local managers have also resorted to various preventive methods to coerce their colleagues to leave the company or accept mobility. These methods were either decided at the level of the management team of [...], under the aegis of the General Management Committee (CODIRG), whose members included Mr [XG] and Mr [FS], or were a direct consequence of the decisions of the management team.*

76. *They state that the personal criminal liability of the accused leaders is based, on the one hand, on the joint decision to adopt such an accelerated staff reduction policy, based on the aforementioned harassment actions, and, on the other hand, on the coordinated implementation of that policy, as well as on close monitoring for three years.*

77. *They conclude that the imperative acceleration of the reduction of staff within a limited timeframe, the methods used, the 'cascade' effects and the 'eviction effect' on employees generated by these methods with anxiogenic consequences, regardless of their fate, despite the warnings of trade unions, including the exercise by six trade unions of a right to*

warn in July 2007 of 'threatening the health of employees', constituted repeated actions, unrelated to normal powers of direction and control.

78. They add that the announcement of suicides, including four only in May 2008, did not prevent the continuation of the NExT plan and ACT programme until the end of 2008.

79. As regards the personal responsibility of the defendants, referring to Mr [XG], they note that he initiated the massive staff reduction plan within a very short period of time and that, during the submission of the plan to the association ... in October 2006, he claimed to be involved not only in the setting of reduction targets but also in the implementation of the necessary control tools and management methods, which resulted on the ground in managerial behaviour aimed at the degradation of working conditions.

80. They explain that he pursued the implementation of that policy, including by giving instructions to exercise 'pressures' which continued, during the period under investigation, despite warnings and which follow up on the request made in 2006 to [C] to implement a 'crisis programme'.

81. They note that Mr [XG] decided to maintain that policy of staff reduction and internal mobility, despite the human damage, even though he was aware of the age structure of the staff and the disappearance of the system of end-of-career leave for officials.

82. As regards Mr [FS], the Judges note that, like Mr [XG], he followed and controlled the operations throughout the period of facts delimited by the First Judges, thus ensuring an effective implementation of the staff reduction, taking care that the objective was distributed and implemented by and for each of the eleven territorial directorates and, in a 2017 interview, admitted that he exerted pressure 'all the time', leaving no room for manoeuvre, and was also aware of initiatives taken at local level by managers.

83. They conclude that the above-mentioned facts demonstrate, on the part of the two defendants, active participation in the commission of the offence, which goes far beyond the mere provision of instructions.

84. Finally, in order to characterise the intentional element, they emphasise, in essence, relying in particular on the statements of Mr [XG] and Mr [FS], on their previous professional experience and on their long-standing and deep knowledge of the company ..., that they acted knowingly and lucidly, pursuing the implementation of the staff reduction policy and assessing its results.

85. They retain the knowledge of Mr [XG] and Mr [FS] of the negative effects of maintaining the method on the health of the group's staff and on their working conditions, their degradation being significantly illustrated by various expert reports which revealed an increase in stress, tensions and discomfort at work, a dislocation/fragmentation of working groups into an almost permanent recomposition, organisational routines to be re-appropriated, staff distress, landmark losses and a failure of systems to prevent psychosocial risks.

86. In so doing, the Court of Appeal characterised, as regards Mr [XG] and Mr [FS], the offence of psychological harassment, which is the main reason for the complicity alleged against Ms [CL]-[VE] and Ms [YM], for the following reasons.

87. In the first place, as regards Mr [XG], the judges considered, by sufficient and uncontradictory grounds and by virtue of their sovereign power of assessment of the facts, that the repeated actions listed by them, which took place throughout the relevant period and

which are illustrated by facts prior to it, constituted a deliberate strategy of harassment devised at the highest level of the company, the implementation of which the accused ensured by positive acts, in a hierarchical line, at the cost of an assumed degradation of the working conditions of all employees, with the result that they rightly concluded that the accused had been guilty of the material element of the offence of psychological harassment, both by its purpose and by its effect.

88. In the second place, as regards Mr [FS], the judges correctly inferred that his actions, as they were assessed as sovereign, which had been carried out over several years and consisted in the implementation, by positive acts, of the company policy defined within the management bodies of ..., which he claimed and for which he took care to implement in the entities of the group under his direction, also constituted the material element of psychological harassment, both by the purpose of his actions and by their effects.

89. Furthermore, in finding that Mr [XG] and Mr [FS] were aware of the negative effects of maintaining the method adopted on the health of the group's employees and on their working conditions, the judges did not fail to characterise the intentional element of the offence for each of the defendants.

90. Thus, the judges established that the decisions taken by the defendants, as well as the public statements which they had made during the relevant period, demonstrating that the group's management exceeded the permissible limits of their respective powers of direction and control, were constituent elements of institutional psychological harassment.

91. Objections can only be rejected.

[...]

III. Possibility of adopting the French solution within the Romanian legal framework

As far as Romanian legislation is concerned, the following should be considered as a preliminary point:

(1) In none of the forms of harassment at work, whether it is provided for in the Labour Code or in G.O. no. 137/2000, it is not required to produce the indicated effect.

In Art. 5 para. (2) of the Labour Code and Art. 2 para. (5¹) of G.O. No. 137/2000 the occurrence of the effect is provided alternatively with the existence of the purpose of producing such an effect, which means that it is sufficient to have this purpose even if the intended effect does not occur.

Art. 2 par. (5²) of G.O. no. 137/2000 stipulates only the condition that the behavior has the ability to produce the undesirable effect and not to actually produce it.

(2) The systematic nature of the behaviour is required only by Art. 2 par. (5²) of G.O. No. 137/2000, and not by par. (5¹) of the same normative act or by Art. 5 par. (2) of the Labour Code.

It is apparent from the grounds of the French judgment that the conduct at issue was systematic within the employer entity. Indeed, it is hard to imagine that the immediate purpose of the deterioration of the working climate, with the purpose and mediated purpose of 'persuading' employees to have the initiative of terminating their employment relationship, would be achieved by a single action or isolated actions.

Systematicity does not necessarily mean that there are several measures taken by the employer; even if it were a single measure, its ultimate aim is to monitor its effects over time, until that aim is achieved, and to take complementary measures to ensure that it is implemented effectively; such a measure, albeit a one-off measure, would acquire the character of a systematic treatment if it were strictly pursued, its infringement would be severely sanctioned, or there would be other enforcement measures on an ongoing basis.

Of course, as was held in the judgment of the French Court of Cassation, there should be other elements capable of leading to the conclusion that, in reality, the employer's purpose is to reduce staff or to obtain an economic advantage and that it is not just the exercise within the legal limits of his right to organize the activity.

In this respect, it should be borne in mind that, as a criminal case, guilt had to be proven in relation to the requirements of the presumption of innocence.

In the field of labour disputes, this requirement is not as high. On the contrary, since this is discriminatory treatment, Article 2(7) of G.O. No 137/2000 provides that an employee who is the victim of psychological harassment in the workplace must prove the factual elements of psychological harassment, the burden of proof being borne then by the employer, in accordance with the law, and the intention to harm by acts of psychological harassment in the workplace must not be proved.

In these circumstances, especially since art.2 al. al. (5²) of G.O. no. 137/2000 expressly refers to groups as well, the employer's systematic actions regarding all employees, including subjecting them to stress and physical exhaustion, could fall under the scope of psychological harassment at work.

However, even if the intention to harm by acts of psychological harassment in the workplace does not have to be proven, in such a particular situation, in which it would not exist individualised persons who would be the victims of that treatment, but institutional harassment, targeting all employees (possibly with some exceptions), there should be a minimum of evidence leading to the conclusion that the aim is to reduce the number of employees or another economic purpose, such as accepting the reduction of salary rights, accepting unpaid additional work, etc. Of course, it is also not excluded that such treatment is the expression of frustration or that it is purely vindictive on the part of employees who acquire managerial positions, but an explanation should be proposed by the complainants and the employer should demonstrate the necessity of the measures taken and the existence of an objective justification for them.

In this regard, it should not be omitted that the plaintiff, before the court, may invoke any means of proof, respecting the constitutional regime of fundamental rights, including audio and video recordings or statistical data on the basis of which the existence of direct or indirect discrimination can be presumed, according to art.27 al.4 of G.O. no.137/2000.

In particular, statistical data may be very relevant if they show, for example, that after starting a certain systematic treatment of employees, a large number of them have resigned or requested the termination of the individual employment contract by agreement of the parties or have requested a move to other structures, possibly with a reduction in salary rights (if, for example, it is claimed that the aim pursued was a certain reorganisation). In such a situation, for example, it would be very difficult for the employer to explain what would have been

another reason why the employees had the initiative of terminating the employment relationship or accepting its modification, possibly under disadvantageous conditions.

In an analysis of this type, in one case, the statistical data communicated by the employer were taken into account, which showed that out of the total number of employees who were on childcare leave, 50.9% of employees changed their work type when returning from leave, and 49.09% of employees terminated their employment relationship with the bank for various reasons, which led to the conclusion that the employer had a human resources policy that systematically disadvantaged employees in this situation. This conclusion was finally reached even though, out of a total of 604 persons who had been on parental leave during the period under review, only 15 persons had terminated their employment relationships as a result of the employer's termination of their employment, while another 309 had retained their previous position when they returned to work, 97 had made lateral movements, 59 had been promoted to higher positions and another 124 had terminated their employment with the bank as a result of their own initiative.⁴ This is because, although apparently it is the initiative and will of the employees, the very large number of employees who, upon returning from parental leave, "choose" to change their job or to terminate their employment relationship makes it unlikely that it is a free personal choice; statistical data can give rise to the presumption that this option was, in reality, forced by the conditions of return to work, various rather informal pressures, other elements of a discriminatory personnel policy; statistically, it is impossible for such a large proportion of employees to have the same option to modify or terminate the employment relationship upon returning from parental leave, especially when it comes to options with negative consequences, without a common cause that can reasonably be assumed to be generated by the only person with whom all employees interact, namely the employer. In this context, it should be borne in mind that promotion to a management position or moving to a different position (even under the same or higher pay conditions) may also be discriminatory treatment in that the employer may seek to subject the employee to a new probationary period and to terminate the individual employment contract under apparently non-discriminatory conditions, under Article 31(3) of the Labour Code, without having to give any reason.⁵

As a result, it is the employer who, in such a context, has to prove the opposite and even that he has active policies for the reintegration of employees in such a situation (in this sense, *mutatis mutandis* the Judgement of the CJEU of 25.04.2013 in the ACCEPT case - C-81/12 par.56, 58).

In the *Di Trizio v. Switzerland* case⁶, the European Court of Human Rights summarised and reiterated its case-law on the evidential value of statistics in the field of discrimination, pointing out that, in principle, statistical data are not in themselves sufficient to reveal a practice that could be classified as discriminatory.

⁴ see CNCD, Decision No 169/03.04.2013 presented and analysed in Anghel, Răzvan, '*Discrimination based on gender in employment relationships. Dismissal as a result of the termination of the employment of an employee who has taken parental leave*' *Revista de Drept Social*, No 1/2016;

⁵ see European Commission, Directorate General for Justice, European Network of Legal Experts in the Field of Gender Equality – 'Fighting Discrimination on the Grounds of Pregnancy, Maternity and Parenthood – The application of EU and national law in practice in 33 European countries', August 2012; 6ECtHR, Section II, Judgment of 02.02.2016 in *Trizio v. Switzerland* (application 7186/09), para.85 available at <https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/?i=001-160692>.

In the Hoogendijk case (judgment of 6 January 2005)⁷ however, the ECtHR held that, where the applicant can establish, on the basis of official statistics which are not at issue, the existence of *prima facie* evidence indicating that a measure, even if established in a neutral manner, in fact affects a significantly higher percentage of a given category, it is for the defendant to prove that that situation results from objective factors unrelated to the discriminatory criterion, due to the fact that, otherwise, it would be extremely difficult for the applicant to prove indirect discrimination.

The ECtHR has established certain principles in relation to the burden of proof in these cases. The Court held in its case-law that States are required, under Articles 11 and 14 of the Convention, to establish a judicial system which provides real and effective protection against discrimination arising from trade union activity.⁸ The ECtHR also held that once the applicant had presented a difference in treatment, the government had to prove that it was justified⁹. As regards what constitutes *prima facie* evidence capable of reversing the burden of proof, the Court considers that such evidence may result from the coexistence of sufficiently strong, clear and consistent presumptions and logical reasoning.¹⁰

Similarly, the allegedly free choice of a large number of employees to terminate the employment relationship or to accept its continuation on less favourable terms, within a short period of time, appears to be implausible if it is supposed to be caused by purely personal reasons, and it can be assumed that it has a common cause, namely a certain treatment instituted by the employer at a certain moment immediately before on the employees.

In any case, the existence of institutional harassment in the workplace must be analysed in a global context, taking into account all the particular aspects, which can be extremely varied, of employment relationships within an employer, taking into account, however, the rules of evidence specific to this matter.

IV. Brief conclusions

An employer's behaviour, which has the purpose or effect of, or is likely to have the effect of, deteriorating working conditions, working climate, subjecting employees to stress and physical exhaustion, creating an intimidating, hostile, degrading, humiliating or offensive environment for employees, even if it does not concern a specific, individualised and identifiable employee, but an indeterminate number of employees, may fall within the notion of harassment at the workplace within the meaning of the Romanian law, being assigned an institutional character when it is the result of programmed actions of the employer, concerted actions of management employees.

Even if, from a legal point of view, the classification of harassment in the workplace as 'institutional' has no legal consequences, it is in itself useful to describe a form of harassment in the workplace that could be considered non-existent if the conditions of the legal rule were related only to individual employees, with the result that, in reality, an indeterminate number of employees receive the same treatment.

The identification in French case-law of a motive for this type of treatment, the reduction in the number of employees avoiding dismissal procedures, shows that this type of harassment at work can exist in employment relationships and must be treated in the same way as individual harassment at work.

7ECtHR (Section I), Decision of 6 January 2005 in the case of Gine Wilhelmina Elisabeth Hoogendijk v. the Netherlands (application no.58641/00), available at <https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng/?i=001-68064>.

8Danilenkov and others v. Russia, no. 67336/01, § 124, ECHR 2009.

9E.g. D.H. et al. v. Czech Republic [GC], no. 57325/00, § 177, ECHR 2007 IV.

10Case Baka v. Hungary [GC], no. 20261/12, § 143, 23 June 2016.